

Academic Recovery Programme

Pitch Deck

Organization of Eastern Caribbean States

Developed by

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What is an ARP?

Pre-pandemic challenges

- The threat of natural hazards, such as hurricanes, flooding, and volcanic activity, leading to schooling interruptions
- Lower academic performance and completion rates among boys
- Inclusion challenges for disadvantaged students and those with special educational needs
- Insufficient resources and training for teachers to deliver online instruction

Pandemic challenges

- Inability to cater to children with special education needs
- Internet connectivity
- Device availability and maintenance
- Inability to reach children in disadvantaged households
- Effectively engaging parents in their children's education

Guiding Principles for designing the ARP

1

Face-to-face learning in a shared space is critical. Technology can enhance, but cannot replace, direct teacher-student interaction.

2

Recruit and train the instructors. Regardless of the how the ARP is delivered, teachers and instructors need to be supported.

3

Design a comprehensive diagnostic assessment tool. This helps teachers and policymakers identify the students most in need of remedial education.

4

Use data to make decisions and track outcomes. Responses and decision making should be based on the best available data.

5

Consider small-scale pilot experimentation before scaling the ARP. Prior to nationwide or regional implementation, small-scale experiments and trials should be carried out locally in each of the focus countries.

6

Targeting and raising awareness. Awareness raising should involve collaboration with stakeholders to ensure that beneficiaries have access to the programme.

7

Make the process participatory.

Get teachers, parents, students, and potential private sector partners involved in the design process.

8

Be flexible and consider students' livelihoods.

Programme design must be relevant to the socio economic, academic and geographical realities of students.

9

Evolve pedagogical approaches.

Aim to improve students' learning outcomes in a system that may not have been optimal for students previously.

10

The programme must give full value for money.

The programme must reach intended beneficiaries in a cost-effective way, with additional consideration given to scaling and ensuring tessellation with existing programmes and activities.

11

Ensure students have the resources needed to participate.

Device and internet access, parental supervision are key resource mechanisms needed to support learning outcomes.

12

Reduce class sizes.

Class sizes of 15 or fewer students have the greatest impact on student learning outcomes, as well as one-to-one tuition approaches.

Vision: a clear vision will articulate the flow from programme activities to desired outcomes, providing a summary of the ARP's logic on how the proposed actions will lead to impact.

The Theory of Change provides a useful framework for understanding how a design to enact change works. Specifically, it illustrates how different parts of the model connect and its potential long- and short-term impact.

BARRIERS

PARENTAL ENGAGEMENT

Parents may sometimes be uncooperative and may not engage with teachers. They may also lack the skills to effectively support their children.

INSTRUCTOR AVAILABILITY

Teachers already have very busy schedules and may lack time to engage in TPD sessions, but they play a major role in delivering and ensuring its success. There are not enough specialist support staff for SPED needs.

BUY-IN

For the programme to be successful, it is crucial for respective member states, MOEs, head teachers, facilitators, teachers, parents, and communities to buy in and actively participate.

ACTIVITIES

DEVELOPMENT

Developing capacity

Teachers will be trained in competencies needed to support academic recovery. Parents also supported.

Resources

TPD guides for facilitators and teachers will be developed. An open-access platform for sharing content will be established.

Collaboration and communication

Teacher communities of practice will be established to foster knowledge sharing. Partnerships between schools, families, communities, and strategic organisations will be strengthened. Monitoring will support evidence-based decision making.

SETUP

DEFINING ARP PRIORITIES

In collaboration with MOEs and stakeholders, identify priority sectors (in this case early grade learners), and identify gaps in and complementarities with existing programmes, such as the ELP.

OUTCOMES

Parents **effectively** supervise their children at home to help close academic achievement gaps.

Teachers attain adequate competences required to teach and assess struggling and marginalised students in a **blended learning context**.

Teachers and schools across OECs member states **collaborate and share best practices**.

Respective ministries of education have a record of students who need help.

Children with **special education needs** are adequately catered for, in a blended learning context.

Community groups and civil society organisations actively participate.

OUTPUTS

ARP IMPLEMENTATION IN MEMBER STATES

The ARP will be implemented in schools. Resources will be made available to parents and teachers to support academic progress. Key community figures and organisations will be invested in and engaging with children's education

IMPACT

Students are **retained and achieve the learning outcomes commensurate to their grade**

Component 1: Supporting teachers and instructors

Peer co-facilitated teacher professional development (TPD) sessions, tailored to the requirements of a blended learning experience (combining face-to-face and technology-mediated learning) have been developed and trialled. Communities of practice and peer support networks will be established. Data on implementation and impact will be gathered and evaluated by the EDMU. This is arguably the central component of the ARP.

The TPD sessions use the Stimulus-Plan-Teach-Reflect model to iteratively develop teaching practice

Component 2: Diagnostic tools

The ARP provides guidance on the use of diagnostic tools to inform pre-teaching, teaching, and re-teaching practices. These tools allow for data-informed analysis of learning outcomes and student needs, particularly for identifying those students who need support in reaching the minimum competencies being taught. These tools are sensitive to the needs of SPED students.

Component 3: SPED

During discussions with teachers and ministry officials it was revealed that SPED students were the most affected during the pandemic in terms of academic loss. Therefore, the ARP makes recommendations for additional supporting staff available particularly to primary schools.

Moreover, SPED is a cross-cutting concern across all materials. For example, two of the TPD sessions developed have been specially dedicated to working with SPED students in the context of academic recovery in order to help teachers address learning loss among SPED students.

Longer-term work towards establishing working partnerships with NGOs (such as [Disabled Peoples' International](#)) may also help address issues of inclusivity.

Component 4: Resource library

The resource library will provide open educational resources and other materials that teachers can access to deliver a range of content. The resource library also provides material useful for SPED students who were the most affected during the pandemic.

In particular, access to open education resources (OERs) and platforms will provide teachers with a range of diverse resources which are readily available for use, and which can also be customised to meet a variety of learning needs.

Component 5: Parental Engagement

Parental involvement involves ensuring children show up to lessons, ensuring children do their assignments, and knowing who to reach out to for assistance. A set of guidance has been developed for parents, helping them to be actively engaged with their children's education. Importantly, parents are encouraged to form active partnerships with their child's school and teachers to support learning. The guidance also acknowledges the importance parental mental wellbeing, and of not overloading parents with an additional burden of compulsory materials. Key forums such as Parent-Teacher Associations also have involvement in engaging parents.

Component 6: Community Engagement

Members of the community (including local professionals) and community-based organisations (such as sports groups, youth clubs, voluntary service organisations, and faith-based organisations) should also be considered stakeholders in children's education. Whether in formalised partnerships or providing ad-hoc support, these groups and key individuals will be engaged to support ARP implementation.

Component 7: Cross-sectoral partnerships

As the ARP is scaled, it is envisioned that communities and education stakeholders at a national level form strategic partnerships with relevant private-sector providers — such as internet providers — to supply key resources and supplies, like data and devices. These will be important to the long-term sustainability of the ARP and also to targeting those in disadvantaged households.

Existing partnerships will be evaluated at a school and national level, with opportunities for new partnerships identified, formalised, and monitored to ensure accountability.

Report that goes with this pitch deck

Haßler, B., Megha-Bongnkar, G., Regis, C., & Blower, T. (2021). *An Academic Recovery Programme for the OECS for the OECS Member States* (OECS Academic Recovery Programme Report No. 3). Open Development & Education. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4555952>. Available from <https://docs.opendeved.net/lib/QM6J57C9>. Available under [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). Commissioned by the Organisation of Eastern Caribbean States, Castries, Saint Lucia.

Further background information

Haßler, B., Adam, T., Blower, T., & Megha-Bongnkar, G. (2021). *Academic Recovery Programmes in the Eastern Caribbean — Literature Review* (OECS Academic Recovery Programme Report No. 1). Open Development & Education. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4555872>. Available from <https://docs.opendeved.net/lib/DZA3GVBD>. Available under [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). Commissioned by the Organisation of Eastern Caribbean States, Castries, Saint Lucia.

Haßler, B., Blower, T., Megha-Bongnkar, G., & Regis, C. (2021). *Academic Recovery Programme: Synthesis of Qualitative Data and High-level Overview* (OECS Academic Recovery Programme Report No. 2). Open Development & Education. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4555874>. Available from <https://docs.opendeved.net/lib/XAMQ949U>. Available under [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). Commissioned by the Organisation of Eastern Caribbean States, Castries, Saint Lucia.

Guidance on implementation

Haßler, B., Megha-Bongnkar, G., Regis, C., & Blower, T. (2021). *Academic Recovery Programme: Concept Note for Implementation* (OECS Academic Recovery Programme Report No. 5). Open Development & Education. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4726106>. Available from <https://docs.opendeved.net/lib/FMVT2NIB>. Available under [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). Commissioned by the Organisation of Eastern Caribbean States, Castries, Saint Lucia.

Final report and summary of all materials

Haßler, B., Megha-Bongnkar, G., Regis, C., & Blower, T. (2021). *Final Report and Recommendations* (OECS Academic Recovery Programme Report No. 6). Open Development & Education. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4603101>. Available from <https://docs.opendeved.net/lib/TD6VRUSA>. Available under [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). Commissioned by the Organisation of Eastern Caribbean States, Castries, Saint Lucia.

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- Adrien Coquet. 'Teacher'. [Link](#)
- Alice Design. 'Family'. [Link](#)
- designexpert61@gmail.com. 'Community'. [Link](#)
- DinosoftLab. 'diagnostics'. [Link](#)
- Razlan Hanafiah. 'wheelchair'. [Link](#)
- Vectors Point. 'ebook'. [Link](#)
- Vectorstall. 'partnership'. [Link](#)

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